

PROCESSING PROBLEM AND SOLUTIONS FOR AN INDUSTRIAL AUTOMATED MICROWAVE CURING SYSTEM FOR A THERMOSET COMPOSITE

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Microwave processing of polymer composites, whilst being able to effect a very fast curing time compared to thermal curing, nonetheless presents unique production problems. The paper reports on the development of a small industrial microwave unit for the microwave curing of a fiber reinforced composite within a high pressure autoclave, the associated problems encountered in the process, and how they can be resolved. This includes the problem of overheating in the process leading to charring or local heating, leakage or inefficient absorption of microwave radiation, void reduction within a microwave curing environment. Control of the process is again unique, since normal DSC or DMA characterization techniques typical for a thermal process is simply inappropriate for microwave curing. The paper also reports on some results obtained for real time characterization during microwave curing, using a modified DMA fixture. The results can be used as a knowledge based databank for the industrial CAM control of the microwave process.

I. INTRODUCTION

RADIATION CURING

Radiation curing has been successfully employed in various applications of polymers [1-2]. The radiation source usually used are Ultra Violet (UV) radiation, gamma radiation from a "live" source such as Cobalt 60, X-Rays and high energy electron beam generated from accelerators in the region of > 1 MeV. UV sources cannot be extensively used because of its limited penetration (about 0.4 mm for epoxies) [1]. Although X-rays are more penetrative, the dose rate obtainable in most X-ray systems are about 500 to 5000 rads/hr. For effective crosslinking to occur in most polymers, the dose would be in the order of 2-10 Mrads. An X-ray system would need an unacceptably long time to cure. Whilst gamma radiation is the most penetrative, it is considered hazardous, due to the continuous nature of its and the long half life. Up to recently, electron beam accelerators provide the most effective radiation curing method. However, the economic cost of a high voltage accelerator has all but eliminated its practical application.

PRESSURIZED MICROWAVE CURING

More recently, microwave curing of thermoset composites has been experimentally shown to be both feasible and viable, the main advantage being its significantly shorter total cure time, and therefore better energy efficiency, as well as the consistency achievable in more intricate components [4]. For example, whilst the normal thermal curing time was 12 h, microwave curing took only less than 10 % of this time for optimal curing [4], with the maximum stress and modulus values exceeding the thermally cured components.

However, to apply microwave curing for industrial production of composite components, there are additional problems to be solved. Manufacturing processes for engineering components made from thermoset composites usually require the optimal achievement of two physical properties. The first parameter is the void content, which for consistent and maximum strengths, should at least be less than 5 % [4-6]. Due to the liquid nature of pre-cured resin systems and their susceptibility to moisture adsorption, voids occur during the heat curing process, dominantly due to the presence of moisture content. Conventionally, void reduction is achieved using a combination of vacuum and pressure [5-6], the vacuum transporting the voids out of the un-cured resin, and the pressure dissolving the rest of the voids still existing. Alternatively, a higher pressure can also be applied in order to eliminate the need to apply vacuum during the curing process [6]. Because of the very high dielectric constant of liquid water, void formation is both accelerated and increased in volume. For this reason, high pressure techniques for void reduction after the composite component has been laid-up becomes more important during microwave curing.

OPTIMIZATION OF CURE

The other property to be optimized is the glass transition temperature, T_g . A proper cure procedure would ensure that the T_g value is both maximized [7-8] consistently throughout the component. For a thermal process, the resin is heated to above the maximum achievable T_g and maintained until such time when the T_g of the matrix resin reaches the maximum value. A typical industrial curing cycle for a hot curing epoxy system, such as an anhydride hardened Bisphenol A ether, would require about 4 h for full gelation to occur, and 12 h at 120 °C followed by 2 h post-curing at 130 °C for full final curing.

For conventional thermal autoclave curing, the composite components are usually inserted into an autoclave and heated up. Due to the considerable heat reservoir within the autoclave, provided the composite component to be cured does not differ too much in thickness, heating will be more or less even, so that curing occurs reasonably consistently. Microwave radiation is able to penetrate glass reinforced composite lay-ups quite considerably. Lower allowable microwave frequencies have better penetration, and the power attenuation is not significant for thicknesses of

up to 10 mm. Unfortunately, the magnetron systems for these lower frequency ranges are costly, compared to the higher 2450 MHz frequency magnetrons, whilst for the higher allowable frequency range of up to 2450 MHz, at low power input, the power attenuation through the composite lay-up may be significant, so that for a given power rating a thicker component section will have a lower curing rate than a thinner section. In this case, for the two sections to have the same curing rate, the total microwave dosage should be increased accordingly for the thicker sections. This problem has been resolved by using a PC controlled and stepper motor driven microwave curing fixture, indicated in figure 1, which can be set up within a high pressure autoclave. Figure 2 is a schematic diagram of the control system set up for the fixture inside an autoclave, with the data acquisition software developed for the system indicated in figure 3.

For a given input power, the speed of the wave guide horn thus determines the total dose of microwave, and so ensures even curing for different thickness. Alternatively, for a given speed, the power input can be increased instantaneously and progressively for an increasing thickness. For curing components with widths larger than the horn width, an X-Y motion is used to replace the existing linear motion system. Experimentally obtained results indicate that for the designed horn system, resolution between cured and uncured sections is only in the order of about 5mm. This can be resolved by having an overlapping exposure of the same 1-2 mm. Figure 4 shows a profile of the cured/uncured areas. A slight but crucial modification of the autoclave was necessary to ensure no microwave leakage occurs. This was done by ensuring that the entire autoclave becomes a complete electrical conduction circuit. To do this, a carbon gasket was used between the autoclave body and its door, to ensure electrical conduction. Port outlets were also inserted with ferrite cores to absorb any microwave that might leak out of the exiting wires.

CONCLUSION

Microwave curing can be industrially utilized for the efficient curing of thermoset composites. The ability to obtain a small void percentage as well as optimal curing can be done using a PC controlled microwave source within a high pressure autoclave.

REFERENCES

1. Larson E G, Spencer D S & Boettcher T E, Properties of Radiation Cured Coatings, Radiat. Phys. Chem. vol 30, No. 1, Pp 11-15, 1987.
2. Markovic V, Technical and Economic Comparison of Irradiation and conventional methods, IAEA-TECDOC-454 report, Int Atomic Energy Agency Vienna, 1988.

3. Boey Y C and Lee T H, Electromagnetic Radiation Curing of an Epoxy/Fiber Glass Reinforced Composite, *Rad. Phy. Chem.*, 38 (4), 1991, 419-423.
4. Stringer L G, Optimisation of the Wet Lay up/vacuum bag Process for CFRP Composites, *Composites*, 20 (5), 1989, 441.
5. Boey F Y C, Reducing the Void Content and its Variability in Composite Specimens using a VIM process, *Polymer Testing*, 9 (6), 1990, p363-379.
6. Boey F and Lye S W, Void Reduction in Autoclave Processing of Composites, Part 1: High Pressure Dissolution of Voids, *Composites*, in print, 1992.
7. Enns J.B. and Gilham J.K., *Polymer Characterization: Spectroscopic, Chromatographic and Physical Instrumental Methods*, ed. Craves C.D., American Chem. Soc., *Advanced Chem. Ser.*, 203, 1983.
8. Enns J.B. and Gilham J.K., Time-Temperature-Transformation (TTT) Cure Diagram: Modeling the Cure Behavior of Thermosets, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 28, 1983, 2567-2591.

Figure 1: PC controlled and stepper motor driven microwave curing fixture.

Figure 2: schematic diagram of the control system set up for the fixture inside an autoclave

Figure 3: Data acquisition software developed for the system indicated in figure 3.

Figure 4: Profiles of cured and uncured areas.